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SUMMARY KEYWORDS

assistant, interpret, nice, feel, bit, grumpy, thinking, string, answers, red hair, vibration, happened, notice, floor, kids, lights, wheelchair, worked, laying, lying

SPEAKERS

Interviewer, Observer 3

Interviewer 00:02

Just because I will forget. Yeah. So how do you think this session went? Just I want to hear your first impressions for starting with the interview.

Observer 3 00:16

I think it I think it went well, I mean, I've done some studies with these children before. And in Nevis, it is like it was like, you cannot get the perfect. Do say like, you have to just take what you get in some way. And it went really well. Like, it seemed like they enjoyed it. And after a while, maybe some of them got a bit tired. That's not, that's not like a strange thing. Because it was like 30 minutes. And that room is quite intense. It's small, and it's warm. And it's like, I think that I imagine like for them to be in there. And that's those lights and sounds and everything is meant to be like to go to you know, amusement park or something. So, after? I mean, it's like natural that they get tired of them.

Interviewer 01:23

Yeah, I mean, from the perspective of an external person as I am, it was, to me as the front two is very difficult to interpret, or to get our feelings. So you

Observer 3 01:36

it is it is, I mean, that's for everyone. I also like, it has so much to do with so many things like who's assisting, you know, like the assistants that were there. Like, they also like, helping in different ways that you could see, they're, like, everyone gets kind of different... eh... how would you say like, [inaudible] Like perhaps perspectives. Not but, you know?

Interviewer 02:17

Okay. If I need to use the dictionary I would use it as well.

Observer 3 02:26

Like you like, prerequisites?

Interviewer 02:29

Oh, yeah, yeah, sure.

Observer 3 02:30

Yeah. Everyone does it a little differently depending on who's helping them, because everyone is like, happy in different ways. That's one thing that I thought about. Maybe, like you need to, you should maybe have circulated assistants as well. But otherwise, I think this, I think we're good. Since the answers, I also like, you interpret their answers. So you don't know if I mean, we can't know what they want to say. But they can try to interpret what they want to say. And if you and that's why I think it's good with videos and samples, you can compare, like, the answers will tell you how they look only like not like facial expressions. And if those matches with the answers, then it's probably higher, like liability to answer them. Because sometimes they say like, "I don't like this, and you can clearly see that they like it [laughs]. So it's a So the answers are somehow Yeah,

Interviewer 03:38

well, they are kids, their kids.

Observer 3 03:40

Yeah. And, and the answers are not super... And everyone's like that they're practicing this picture language in school, everyday, a lot of but some of them are, are older and practice longer. And what I mean, some students, they just try to, you know, to get them to have a clear way to say yes or no. So it's really hard to know what what they want to express sometimes that we have to try to, like interpret it... because I think it's really important that we do these things with them and that they can be a part of the studies because and we have to, like interpret because otherwise they wouldn't be able to participate at all. And that would be will be very good.

Interviewer 04:40

Yeah. I mean, from the outside it looked like like they were very chilled. Like they weren't like agitated. I was worried because I was filming. And I was worried that perhaps like having my camera in front of them would disturb them.

Observer 3 04:57

Ne...

Interviewer 04:57

But I was okay. I think that One of them would they were a bit shy, but perhaps is misinterpreting. I don't know, to be honest this really hard to know

Observer 3 05:07

it's also like, it's also good for like to be some persons that hasn't met them before. I guess that's also really valuable, because then you don't have any, like, pre thoughts about how they are going to. Yes, yeah.

Interviewer 05:25

So, so that's interesting. So what, uh, I don't know if a [Observer 1] introduced you or told you like, the way that these kinds of interviews function work?

Observer 3 05:38

No, I don't.

Interviewer 05:39

Okay. So this, I will do a micro phenomenological interview. And it has like this weird name. Where basically, is what we will do. And we will try to decide this together. These kinds of interviews is like, instead of having a specific question, you pick a moment that you found interesting during the interaction for kids, just pick one. And you describe it. And it's this is like taking a microscope, we're trying to go expanded and expanded and expanded. So what's gonna happen is that we will try to get into the details of what you were feeling during that interaction with the kids, and how you were interpreting this and the things that we were thinking, and all the associations that came during the moment, that specific moment that you found interesting. So what's gonna happen is sometimes I will ask you several questions about how it was so how, what's around you, so we will try to go back to this moment sort of recreated? So some of the questions might be repetitive. This is like an annoying, that's part of it. They don't want to like make you feel annoyed. But yeah, it can be like a little bit repetitive. But how was it? And I will ask you... really how it was? And also we're not it's not that important to like, focus on aspects related to technical issues, or it's more like what you were feeling because for us is important, your perspective as an educator, because, you know, there's some I mean, we were talking that it's hard to interpret how they think, but still, do you sort of you, you know them better. So you still have something you you're able to sort of say and tell me? Yeah, well, they were like, fine. At the end, we're tired. But there's something in you that knows that. So that's interesting to us. So, I will ask you, if you are, of course, if you are tired, and... you're free to stop interview anytime. Okay. It could happen as well. So I was thinking it could last between forty minutes to one hour. If that's okay.

Observer 3 07:58

Yeah.

Interviewer 08:00

So, what else is? Yeah? So, I will ask you, if you agree, to think.. or we can think together and then we can try to expand it and see what happens. And experience that you... was a moment in your experience this morning that you found interesting, for example, that the kids like you noticed that one of the kids was really happy or was like not that happy? I don't know.

Observer 3 08:32

Yeah, it was very nice when you had the girl like that was like... And like if when like the control room was here, then or handle strings and she was over here by the mirror.

Interviewer 08:51

Okay.

Observer 3 08:54

And she was on the floor. She she almost looks like she's sleeping in them. Do understand who I mean do red hair.

Interviewer 09:02

Like a girl with the red hair? I thought you were talking about the blonde girl.

Observer 3 09:07

No. Yeah, she also she also did, too. But no, I was talking about the other girl.

Interviewer 09:13

There was like closer to the entrance.

Observer 3 09:15

Exactly.

Interviewer 09:15

Oh, yeah. Okay.

Observer 3 09:19

It was nice because when she was on the floor, and she had the vibrations and when the assistant asked afterwards where she felt that I saw that she picked... I think it was like the back or the bum and, and also the head and that felt like accurate since she laid down. and had her body on it. And also it was the cheek against the floor. So that was nice. It's always nice when you get to get like some liability... feel like the answers are in some way really accurate. That was nice and also like that she actually started to... like the the person that the assisted her was first at first like very, she, she just like hugged her a lot

Interviewer 10:15

and what happened with her?

Observer 3 10:16

there were the assistant sat like very close, like hugged her, like, think so and then I told her like, maybe you can come back up a little bit. So she can explore stuff. And I think it worked out quite well because she started to, like, explore the string and then she lay down on the floor, but it was a that was nice.

Interviewer 10:46

So anything else to add from that situation? Okay, so I'll try to like repeat back to you and see if there's anything that you find it's wrong or not quite right. So you can correct me if I'm wrong. So you were talking about this girl that was next to the to the mirror and had red hair. Right. Okay. So she was you said at the beginning in that she had a gesture that was almost like sleeping? Yeah. Okay. Before that, when this thing started, the person, the assistant was sort of hugging here. I think you said kissing her. And I'm very sure, but it was hugging her. And then you said that perhaps you should like go a little bit back so she can interact with the string. And you notice that she was like laying on the ground, laying

down with her cheek on the floor. And sort of feeling the vibration, which was nice. Because when she was asked about the responses she picked, like the back and the bump, apparently and the head. So it was like a correspondence between, like, what she was doing. And like her responses, right.

Observer 3 12:09

Exactly. Yep.

Interviewer 12:10

Okay. So if you agree, I will ask you to first of all, you remember how was the room during the moment then when she was laying down? And you said it was nice. Can you tell me how was the room? So it was dark? How was it?

Observer 3 12:32

Yeah, it was yeah, the lights were off. And you could see the light the strings were glowing, but the lights were in the ceiling. It was quite like I felt like it was quite a calm feeling room.

Interviewer 12:55

Could you see her face?

Observer 3 12:59

Looks like she, I think she she was just like relaxing things. And sometimes with open eyes. And sometimes with closed eyes

Interviewer 13:12

when she had like the eyes open, and so she had sometimes the eyes open and sometimes their eyes closed. Like she looked calm, tranquil. So the lights were off, the string was glowing, and it was very calm. And she was like laying down. So I would ask you if you agree to go back to the moment when she was like lying down yet with the cheek, like, on the ground. And you felt that it was nice. So how you feel that? how was it?

Observer 3 13:52

I remember that it's not like oh, that's nice that she she stopped... like she made some you know, she was a little bit like... not enough angry, let's say like not though.

Interviewer 14:15

Like grumpy?

Observer 3 14:16

Yeah, yeah, exactly. Exactly. Grumpy. Because she thinks she wanted to... she really likes a wheelchair, like I'm and so she wanted to make play with it. And then the assistant moved it because it wanted her to focus on their on their string and so that's... and I know that sometimes that can... when she start to be like that. She can be quite hard to... you know, to get to do... want to do the task again. But she... just stopped in them to lied there and it was there seem... there seem a very comfortable with the situation. That was nice.

Interviewer 15:04

So, you said that there was a moment that you sort of perceived that she was a little bit grumpy because she was upside up. She likes like being in a wheelchair.

Observer 3 15:16

She liked Yeah, let's like okay, playing with it

Interviewer 15:22

so she likes playing with a wheelchair. But this time she was like on a floor so she was a little bit grumpy right.

Observer 3 15:31

But then it stopped and she just accepted that to be there on the floor and started.

Interviewer 15:37

Okay, so I'll ask you, if you agree. You said that she was a little bit grumpy. So how do we know she was grumpy?

Observer 3 15:46

Because she would made like Grumpy noises like [make noises]

Interviewer 15:55

making grumping noises

Observer 3 15:56

Yeah, and she does like [make other noises]... when a bit angry. She has red hair. So she is strong... to... she's quite the... she's one of the students that is quite... that it's quite like, it's quite clear what they want and don't want.

Interviewer 16:19

Okay,

Observer 3 16:20

if she doesn't agree to a situation she would tell you.

Interviewer 16:24

So. Okay, so. Okay, so she does this like Grumpy. Like, yeah, like just just, like not happy with the situation.

Observer 3 16:34

Exactly.

Interviewer 16:35

Okay, and so do you remember what happened? Exactly. So she's, she's grumpy. She's like Do you remember how was like the exact moment is very strange question because it's like trying to connect with that moment. The exact moment when she started like, stop being grumpy and became like, calm. Can you describe it? Take your time, but

Observer 3 17:11

I think it was maybe when. I'm not I'm not 100% sure when it was exactly what it feels like when the lights were turned off. Because I think the grumpiness was the lights were on and they move the wheelchair away. And this is a bit grumpy and then the turn the lights off and then she probably lie down.

Interviewer 17:38

And she was laying down. Could you describe her? How was she like, what did you see?

Observer 3 17:47

Huh? She looked relaxed and... I'm not sure. I mean, she was like, it looks a little bit uncomfortable. But I don't think that she was uncomfortable. Like I wouldn't have been comfortable I'm in a position but I don't think she has a problem with it. So next is really like a [inaudible... then laughing]

Interviewer 18:29

so you're saying that she looked okay, so it feels like apparently when the lights went off, she started like to sit down and she got calm. And she looked relaxed. But also you said that perhaps a little bit uncomfortable.

Observer 3 18:47

No, I not. Not really uncomfortable. I mean, in just thinking about how it looked like I think she was lying with like, you know her her lips in some this position [like this] and so maybe if you would have a picture of the thing "Oh, that looks... that's uncomfortable but I don't think that she was uncomfortable".

Interviewer 19:07

Okay.

Observer 3 19:10

And I also think that he probably was like, feeling it. I think it looked like she felt like this vibrations and like maybe that she was like analysing what it was. I think that she was the only one I could... or maybe also just really small was really thin one. He was also that I felt like... Yeah, I think he feels like he really feels a lot the vibrations, but now yeah.

Interviewer 19:51

How do you... Okay, so you think that she was feeling the vibration?

Observer 3 19:56

I think so, well I can't be sure but he was so still... you know, she was so still didn't. Didn't know. And that makes me think that she might have thought about like I was... trying to feel and trying to understand.

Interviewer 20:18

Or you think perhaps she was wondering what was happening, that she was trying to feel like the vibrations?

Observer 3 20:24

Yeah, like, you know, she was lying around like opening her eyes but like... she looks a bit like, you know, when someone's listening for sound...

Interviewer 20:37

like someone listening.

Observer 3 20:38

Yeah, but... a.... yeah

Interviewer 20:44

then how does someone? How's that look when someone's listening to a sound?

Observer 3 20:54

Maybe like that you did you look but you don't have any particular place where... you don't look at anything, but you look.

Interviewer 21:13

So it's like when you look at something at the same time, you're not looking at something? Yeah. It's like it's kind of sight.

Observer 3 21:21

Like, your eyes are open, but you don't like look at anything special. And I think that I... when I think that I'm listening to something, I probably like relax my jaw as well. If you want to like no... I think it's like when you're listening for a sound and want to localize where it is. And that's what's kind of the impression I got from her as well. Like, okay, feel this, where is it from?

Interviewer 22:00

So, just to recap, she was she was like still. And you think that at some moments she was like wondering how was the vibration? You could see that.. like, she was like feeling opening their eyes closing their eyes. It was like, she was really trying to listen. And this listening, like, quality comes when you look at things; it's like looking but with no without looking. So perhaps a new case when you listen, also, it might happen that the jaw is relaxed. So it's like looking but and looking at anything special, but feels like,

Observer 3 22:41

yeah, we can be like comparable to feeling that... trying to localize the sound. But like she was it felt like maybe she was thinking about, like trying to localize how this vibration happened, like where they've come from. And then I mean, she saw like, I don't know if she I'm not sure if she like connected the... because it was the assistant mostly that pull the string, when she saw when she did it, and she heard the sounds like that's probably also have seen that there was a sound and the vibration and like, you hear the sound and you feel it and like trying to get that connection. Maybe she was thinking about it.

Interviewer 23:27

Okay. So yeah, because the assistant was actually like playing with the string, right.

Observer 3 23:35

So she didn't do the string infection herself. But she heard the sound and felt the vibration and yeah... if you don't, that's.... that could mean if you... it is quite straight, if you like imagine to... not understand, like not really a get what.... But if you don't pull the string and you don't really get by I hear a sound and then this vibrate, I probably makes you think it would make me think as well if I just I didn't really know where it came from.

Interviewer 24:10

Oh, I see. So you think this correspondence between, like the vibration, the sound, if you don't know where it's coming from that will make you choose... to try to localize where is that from?

Observer 3 24:23

So yeah. I mean, I can only think about how I would...

Interviewer 24:28

Yeah, sure.

Observer 3 24:29

...we'll do. Like if I didn't understand how it was like where it came from, and I just found them here. They would try to like...

Interviewer 24:45

okay, so and perhaps you think that she was like, perhaps try to do that.

Observer 3 24:50

Yeah. Yeah. Because she, like thing I said earlier about like, I think she looked like she was... yeah, like listening, thinking about something? Because you're... Yeah, because she was... like not moving very much. So I can think that's maybe a sign up like, concentration.

Interviewer 25:19

So she wasn't moving very much. It's a sign of concentration. How do you know that?

Observer 3 25:24

I don't know. But I imagine like if I, if I was gonna try to, like, feel and hear something and understand it, I would like to still and try to just... when is it coming I like waiting for it to happen again. This if if I was if I was, I would moving around them, it would be harder to localize where it came from. That's probably it.

Interviewer 25:56

Yeah, I see. And you said that, okay, so she was laying on on the ground, and she was listening that it was something like in her face, it seems that she was trying to make sense of this like, localizes sound. So she's looking like, she was like, looking at the sound knowing. So and you said that, at the beginning, you mentioned that the assistant was at some point... asked her like to... sort of assess her experience. Right? With with this starts. Do you remember what happened exactly before that?

Observer 3 26:34

I think that but yeah... she was asked if she liked it or not first talking. And And before she was asked if she liked it or not, the assistant helped her set up to make it like, easier to ask and to get an answer. As humans have played on the floor, and then after she liked it, not, I think almost geology certain selected, and then just wearing the body. And then she pointed, she pointed like with your face on the pictures. And then that's usually how, how she does it. And then there's a sentence like, which one of these they had took away the pictures with the head? And I'm not 100% sure if it was like but I think it was the back end a bar I think that was the same picture. And to hold up only those two and asked which one and then she I heard that she interpreted the shoes, the one with the back. But I think that you really could make it was so accurate with with both of them. Since you're most likely on the floor then she probably felt a little face. And when she shows both both in the start, I think that you could interpret that as both as well. But in the on the Mac systems, I probably just like max out one of them

Interviewer 28:46

so they're saying that so she was shops to sit up. And she was asked whether to like it or not. And you are almost sure that she said that she liked it. And then when she was asked where in the body she like she pointed with her face. And she took away the picture of the face in the back

Observer 3 29:21

The assistant....

Interviewer 29:22

yeah, the assistant took away the pictures of the face on the back and holds boths. And it seems that she picked the one on the face.

Observer 3 29:35

No, no, but like, when I looked I would have said that the two peoples but the assistant that helped her and that [drama mum]. She said Okay, thank you. She was the one with back. So and this is like one of the things that... yeah, it's like hard to interpret what they're saying. So the two positions are different, like for different people, but then you're gonna interview some of the assistants?

Interviewer 30:10

I would love to,

Observer 3 30:11

because I like to get some kind of like right reliability to the results, you probably have to try and collect lots of different answers from different persons. Like if you should ask me and, and one of the assistants and, and [Observer 1], and maybe we have three different descriptions, but some things are similar and that's probably a good way to get more.

Interviewer 30:38

Yeah, sure.

Observer 3 30:39

Accurate. Yeah, answers maybe because no one can. That's like the thing that no one can no one can say for sure. Like what another person say, they can't tell you which words is not very good. Sometimes hard, even if you can speak understand it.

Interviewer 30:54

Yeah. It is really depends. But still, it's very valuable, that you you know them. I mean, for example, I wouldn't be able to tell that she was grumpy or happy. For example, perhaps I would have but I wasn't looking at her. Bur that comes from an experience that you have, you feel like are able to say "Okay, she was fine. She was like, lying on the floor. And she was saying that she was okay." So it's still there. It's like, you know, things. There's a level of motivation.

Observer 3 31:29

Like Yeah, I mean, it's hard to say that like No, but it's like I can I can make to be quite accurate. I hope hopefully.

Interviewer 31:41

Yeah, I think more informed guests.

Observer 3 31:45

Yeah. I mean, that's I thought about this so much like it's impossible to notice other person's feelings it's like... but you we have to try to interpret anyway like I said in the beginning it's it's like so important to do this kind of stuff studies together.

Interviewer 32:10

Yeah. Okay, so. Okay, so do you remember what happened when? So she was trying to localize the sound and she was... the assistant helped her to sit up. So you remember how she. How was the girl? was happy to be up to? Was she happy to like being sitting up? Or was she like, wanted to keep like lying down? Do you remember?

Observer 3 32:48

Maybe she was a little bit like yeah you know, she had been lying there for a couple of minutes and then she is seated up? Like "aghh". We could we have like, rested for a while and then... I don't know if

she was like... Maybe Maybe she was a little bit tired. When assistant showed her pictures she was like, so that she was like lying forward like doing some sound like "awhh" and I don't think it was like a really it wasn't that grumpy as the name says. Little bit like "ahhh" maybe [laughing]. I don't know what words to use to describe it but yeah, looked a bit tired. You know, sometimes I experienced that as well. Like, you know, it's just getting tired of everyone. Okay, I'll do it one more time. Maybe like that when she... when she helped her to sit up.

Interviewer 34:22

And you also said at some point you said that okay. So this happened. So you were looking at her and she was like closing the eyes, opening the eyes and then listening. When she was helped to be seated up, and she pointed with the face to like those places that were activated. And you you said that it felt nice. That "ah. ok"

Observer 3 34:47

Yeah, I felt really I was like...

Interviewer 34:51

could you please describe how was like this feeling of niceness? How did you feel it? Very interested in knowing.

Observer 3 35:01

It just like it's such a it's often like such a, like, how do you say like, very, very cool thing? From from most of them like... And when... when they say something, it's like, when they say something that you really, really like, yeah, that's such an accurate answer. That's exactly what she should have felt because it was those parts of the body that was like on the floor. And so the answer was really, really accurate. And that makes me think that's maybe she wanted to actually want to say that. To ask them a lot of things like, often... it's often that you don't... I think that they, they find it quite hard to use the pictures and talk with them. Like, you know, like, if we are... like taking a class and you you feel like new on the subject, and maybe you don't like, you've maybe not the first like, on raise your hand or the teacher asked you something. I think that's a feeling that they get, like, they have to learn this. And they're training a lot, but it goes quite slow. And so often, many of them also just like, you know, they don't want to use it the yeah, probably because they think it's hard... so it's, it's so nice to see when something is like accurate. And it has happened sometimes also, knowing someone is using this book, they have like a booklet filled with pictures that is supposed to work like language. And sometimes when someone tells you something that we didn't know, and then maybe we get confirmation from the parents. Yeah, but yeah, we did that yesterday, or yes, we, we had done for them. And that's like the, that's really nice. We have worked so much with this communication, things. And there's also so there's always, like, very small progression that like you have to look for. So it's very nice to see.

Interviewer 37:21

And how do you know this when the kids are making small progressions?

Observer 3 37:28

How I know that they make

Interviewer 37:29

Yeah, how do you notice like when they making like,

Observer 3 37:33

I mean, I think that like, like that situation today is a sign of some kind of progression, like every time they say something is only can also be just like, when they ask for the this communication book themselves. That's also like, really nice. Because like they they show that they want to tell you something. also, that you just get along so maybe tried a long time to understand how to say yes or no, a new get to how it is a yes or no, that was really, like, it's very good to be able to say some of the things. I think that like when you when they when they make when they try to communicate on their own initiative in nice, when they say things that's accurate it's really nice, and so...for some of them, some of them that maybe never want to even answer, but then you can maybe get an answer that can also be an essential like progression in their learning. That's nice.

Interviewer 38:51

And just thinking you said it feels nice I can imagine that feels nice because it's like reestablishing this communication it's really hard to really know what they think but they feel this isn't strange question I know but where your body feels this nice sensation, where it happens

Observer 3 39:19

here

Interviewer 39:25

do you think that the kids realize that we feel fine

Observer 3 39:30

yeah, yeah, I think so. I think they're probably they probably quite sensitive to a lot of... know how do you say like vibrations neuro because like if someone I mean just if someone is blind they develop very good hearing and so on. So since they miss other like, they don't they miss some quite A lot of functions that most people have. So they probably develop others. That's I don't know which ones but there could be one thing that sensing So, yeah, and this for this particular time, I don't know, I was like, behind. And she was also more focused to the assistant that was with her but yeah, I think they're, they're good at something like energy.

Interviewer 40:40

And how do you know that they are good at sensing? He said,

Observer 3 40:47

I don't I mean, I don't know. But yeah.

Interviewer 40:52

How do you feel it's

Observer 3 40:54

like, you can often you can often like affect the level of (I think it's called affect) level of their affect by being like, if someone someone like, I get tainted or something, you can just, you can often make them, like, calm down just by being calm. And they also, you know, like in small children, you know, if you have like a group of small children and one starts to cry everyone else. That happen... a lot like that they feel how the other persons in the room are feeling and then they, they feel the same.

Interviewer 41:47

And if you notice that this that actually happened some points during some point, experience Yes, just an example. I was filming one of the kids. And I think that the boy that was with the soft toy, this little one and was very, very active. I think that he was a little bit that he made like a little scream, like, nothing like that. And all the kids like notice that now. Yeah, so I was wondering if you felt at some point that she got distracted by, like, the other kids state or [inaudible] happen?

Observer 3 42:40

No, I don't think you know, just particularly like not more than than anyone else, which is, okay.

Interviewer 42:54

Let me take the time. Okay, so I will recap your experience. And so... you were mentioning situation with the girl with the red hair. And what's next to the mirror wasn't a foreigner, and was with the assistant who was like playing with string actually. But well, before that, the girl was kind of a little bit grumpy because she was in a wheelchair. And then it was like put on the ground. And he was like, making some grumpy noises. She does when she's not very happy about things. But then apparently, when the lights turned off, she calmed down. And so the assistant was like playing with string, right? So this girl was laying down and feeling the vibrations. Her like her jaw was relaxed. And she was opening and closing their eyes. Like she was looking at something and not looking... like kind of localizing like what the where the sound that vibration was coming perhaps like this correspondence between the two. Because again, there was the assistant who was like playing with with a string and you think that perhaps you was trying to figure out like, make sense of that. So then the light was on. And so the assistant helped her to sit her up. And so I think she did a couple of grumpy noises [I imitate some noises] and so she was asked if she liked it or not. And she said yes. Apparently. Then she also with the cards she pointed with her face on both the back and the face and finally the assistant pick the back as like, like the response okay so and what happened after that after?

Observer 3 45:18

the that you got the answers.

Interviewer 45:21

Yeah. And you feel it felt nice and then it was like okay the answers are here

Observer 3 45:26

Hmmm [pause] You should probably... you could probably see it in the order. Yeah, I'm not I'm not 100% Sure. It must have been a second last time. Right. It sounds like the last round everyone was. And that's also like when a typical situation where you know, when the teacher was like, yeah, so

everybody knows. I don't know if you've picked up but like, sorry, very nice. The buses are leaving for everyone. So then it gets quite tense. And that sort of last session was good. Yeah. That feeling was spreading in the room that there was some kind of stress so that that must have been what happened after that there was this last time and and distress leveling, addressed it? Yes. It was not so much time left. But I'm not sure if he was if she was very, like affected. I think that that I was really kind of divided. So I don't remember exactly what they did. That was five minutes.

Interviewer 47:09

But you felt that the room was affected in some ways?

Observer 3 47:13

Yeah, really? Like

Interviewer 47:14

yeah, I don't speak Swedish. But I've noticed the thing that I've noticed was that everything was calm and went from one second to another. Everybody was like picking things up, and packing. Yeah. Okay. Yeah. It was kind of interesting.

Observer 3 47:32

Because the the this busses to take them back to school was supposed to be there. I think it was 10.40 and the last test was finished maybe 1035. Okay.

Interviewer 47:52

Okay, so I think that close to new here, but I was wondering, is there anything else you might want to add? We haven't like talked about related to that particular experience

Observer 3 48:12

is what it was selected for the experience that we talked about that with the same student yesterday, on the first day. When she was in the wheelchair, she was crying. She was looking at like, the mirrors. And, and she got I thought about them, she went pretty, like distressed about the mirror thing. So she almost didn't notice the string just looking at like this infinity things, through the mirrors but otherwise, I don't know. But like, I think it's important to think about that there's probably a lot of impressions when I'm not sure. Like anything I submitted that it's like maybe it's not for everyone but for some of them may be slightly... what's going on. Like not a roller coaster, but do you know, do you know like, just to get into that feeling like you know when you go back you notice houses where they have like funny mirrors so they probably because quite tired. Yeah, that's maybe why they started up a little bit. And then also I think that as I said, they are really I think that they are quite sensitive to other people's like stress and stuff. So when they're when they're adults, they're starting to be like, Oh my God, we have to... but overall, I think there was a really good session. I mean, right everyone like I think that all students played with a string and some time I saw everyone like doing it by themselves. And that's that's really

Interviewer 50:09

Yeah, yeah. No. They weren't like, they weren't apparently I don't know, correct me if I'm wrong, but I noticed that they were sometimes distracted, sometimes into it, sometimes, like, sort of, no, I don't want to do this. And then it's like, okay. Yes. Was like, kind of. That's what I've noticed from the kids.

Observer 3 50:29

Yeah, yeah, that's, I think the same. I mean, that's probably also what most kids don't they have a shorter attention span than

Interviewer 50:48

well even happens to anyone not only kids! And do you think they were distracted by the fact that we're other other adults that they didn't know?

Observer 3 51:00

I don't know. Maybe. I'm a bit unsure. But, you know, the blonde girl she was, I think a little bit like she was a bit shy.

Interviewer 51:09

Yeah.

Observer 3 51:11

She was like, I think so. So maybe she was on the other side of the country.

Interviewer 51:18

Yeah, I noticed I was filming her I would move to the other side and she.. "don't don't". In an area like, okay, she doesn't want to be found. So I felt a little bit like, yeah, I don't want to film someone that doesn't want to be filmed.

Observer 3 51:43

But then she stopped, apparently. Yeah. And I sometimes I think, you know, it's such a good to do something. So if you're not 100% comfortable.

Interviewer 51:50

Sure.

Observer 3 51:50

It doesn't. Doesn't hurt. Yeah, you're right. helps to develop some personality, in contact with the outside world.

Interviewer 52:02

Okay, anything else?

Observer 3 52:10

I said to [Observer 1] and [Observer 2] that you should try to like sit down. If they hadn't returned, and we say we should try yourself to like, sit on it and see if you feel more vibrations. So I'm not sure how much you feel. It's like, from before,

Interviewer 52:33

That sound amazing. So yes.

Observer 3 52:37

Because then you can I mean, if you try it yourself, you can you at least you know, how it how it feels?

Interviewer 52:42

Yeah, sure. Yeah, I was thinking it depends on the sensitivity of the kids as well. They might be some that are super sensitive. There's others that are not very sensitive, and they don't float that much in me that a lot of vibrations you feel like excited. Okay. Thanks so much for your responses. Yeah.

Observer 3 53:09

And you can just like, tell me if you want to ask anything.

Interviewer 53:15

Okay. Yes. Yeah, I will think I'll think if I have any other questions, can I contact you? Yeah.

Observer 3 53:21

Yeah.

Interviewer 53:22

Thank you. Yeah. You are amazing!

Observer 3 53:23

No worries. It's really good for me as well. To do this, I'm gonna do a study with with where my master's thesis project, maybe next month or something, and this gave me some, some more ideas about how to do that. So it's good for me. And I like to sort of always like, interesting to talk about and get some new views on stuff.

Interviewer 53:23

Yeah, it's amazing. So you're working here KTH now

Observer 3 53:54

In my masters

Interviewer 53:55

yes. Yeah. Yeah. Okay. And you're working with kids.

Observer 3 53:59

I have worked with them for like I think I started working there for like 10 or 11 years ago. But for some reason I started to study here for almost six years. So then I've just worked like on the breaks and then I have this and then... on Thursday mornings I have a class in horseback riding.

Interviewer 54:29

oh nice

Observer 3 54:32

so I made some of them.

Interviewer 54:35

But it means that some of the kids so do you have been working with them for 11 years? So are the same kids or?

Observer 3 54:42

Eh, no, I think that those who were there today I'm I've known everyone except the the small, the little guy and And now the other three I have known for a long time since, like the red hair girl the first time, so she was six and I think he's 14. So, and the same with the blonde girl, but she's probably 16.

Interviewer 55:21

So it's interesting because I thought all the blonde girl must be like a teenager. We've seen a very teenager attitude. And now that you're saying that they go with a red hair as well like "ahh, I don't want to respond to your question"

Observer 3 55:50

but I've known him for a long time, so that's good. And also the big boy. I don't know how old he is now, but he's probably he's probably like, maybe even older than longer.

Interviewer 56:11

The boy that was sitting next to her actually, like in the middle.

Observer 3 56:15

Yeah, yeah, exactly. Like next to they're not really thin boy, but the other one.

Interviewer 56:20

Yeah, okay. He's also teenager.

Observer 3 56:23

Yes... I am not sure. He's like I'm not sure how you cannot predict. I would guess. So. Yeah, yeah, I think so.

Interviewer 56:42

Do you want a cup of tea because you're in a rush perhaps next time. Hopefully [inaudible]. Okay,